

AI Robo-Advisor Adoption Impact on Financial Inclusion, Financial Literacy, and Investment Habit of Millennial and Gen Z Retail Investor in Indonesia

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Abstract—The emergence of artificial intelligence (AI)-driven robo-advisors (RA) is a key innovation in the financial sector. RA is a digital platform that provides automated algorithm-driven financial planning and portfolio management at a fraction of the cost of traditional advisors, thus democratizing professional portfolio management for the masses market. This study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the role RA plays in transforming modern investment practices and enhancing the financial well-being of this digitally-native demographic. The data is analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), the analysis confirms a positive and statistically significant relationship between the adoption of Robo-Advisor (RA) and Financial Inclusion (FI). However, the study found no significant relationship between RA adoption and Investment Habit (IH). This non-significant result highlights a critical insight: while technology effectively addresses barriers related to access and information, it does not automatically address the behavioral discipline necessary for forming consistent investment habits. This research highlights a clear path for future investigation into the behavioral aspects of FinTech adoption and presents a challenge for FinTech developers. To truly enhance long-term financial well-being, platforms may need to bridge the gap between providing access and fostering consistent action by integrating more effective behavioral touch and self-control influences.

Index Terms—artificial intelligence, robo-advisor, financial technology, financial literacy, financial inclusion, investment habit

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of artificial intelligence (AI) has evolved from early rule-based systems to deep learning models [1]. This transformation has profoundly impacted the financial industry which has enthusiastically adopted AI for tasks ranging from predictive risk modeling and algorithmic trading to sentiment analysis using Natural

Language Processing (NLP) [2]. AI's function in finance changed from being a supplemental tool to a crucial innovation to the operational effectiveness and strategic decision-making help in significant institutions across the globe as its capabilities increased [3].

Robo-advisor being a digital platform that offers automated algorithm-driven financial planning and portfolio management is one of the most important AI-driven breakthroughs in the retail investment sector [4]. To optimize returns for a specific degree of risk, these systems build diversified investment portfolios. Prominent FinTech firms in Indonesia, such as Bibit, Ajaib, and Bareksa, have effectively adopted this technology, indicating a significant change in the wealth management scene [5] [6].

The development of robo-advisor is particularly impactful in emerging economies like Indonesia. Indonesia presents a compelling opportunity with its large young population with high mobile phone penetration and gig economy [7]. Despite these conditions, investor penetration in the capital market remains remarkably low. This gap between a digitally-native population and relatively low investor highlights a massive untapped market from potential investors who have been excluded from traditional wealth management services [6].

Robo-advisors help to widen the access to sophisticated investment strategies by offering professional portfolio management with very low minimum investment knowledge requirements [1]. By making investing more accessible, their user friendly interfaces are specifically designed to appeal to Millennial and Gen Z who make up the vast majority of new investors in Indonesia and

prefer digital platforms for their financial needs. [6] [7]. The primary purpose of this research is to examine the growing importance and impact of robo-advisor adoption within the retail investment landscape especially among younger generations. This study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the role robo-advisors play in transforming modern investment practices and enhancing the financial well-being of this demographic.

Specifically, this study will focus on three primary objectives:

1. To distinguish the impact of robo-advisor adoption on the financial literacy of young investors whether these platforms function as educational tools or simply as automation services.
2. To analyze how robo-advisors enhance financial inclusion by examining their effectiveness in lowering traditional barriers to entry, such as high costs and portfolio complexity.
3. To determine the extent to which the consistent use of robo-advisor influence the development of disciplined and long-term investment habits among retail investors.

II. LITERATURES STUDY

A. Robo-Advisor

A robo-advisor (RA) is a digital platform that provides automated investment advice and financial services to investors typically with minimal human intervention and at a lower cost than traditional wealth advisors [4]. RA represent a key innovation enabled by the ongoing integration of artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), and big data analytics in the financial sector [2]. AI-driven systems use algorithms and deep neural networks to process massive data sets. They detect market anomalies and provide actionable signals in real-time [1][3]. While this automation increase the access to sophisticated portfolio management, the use of complex AI models also poses challenges such as, the lack of explainability (black box problem) and algorithmic biases that highlights the need for transparent model design [5].

B. Financial Literacy

Financial literacy (FL) describes the crucial knowledge and skills required to make informed financial decisions and achieve long-term financial goals [9]. It involves understanding basic economic concepts, investment products, investment standards, and the companies that provide relevant services. In the digital age, higher financial literacy is closely related to the adoption of financial technologies (FinTech) [4]. This competency

allows investors to understand the processes behind the algorithms by seeing through the specific techniques (such as algorithmic trading) and thus take full advantage of digital financial instruments [10]. Individuals with higher literacy tend to have more proactive and diversified investment practices and are better able to navigate complex market dynamics.

H1: RA has a significant relationship with FL

C. Financial Inclusion

Financial inclusion (FI) is the principle of providing all individuals and businesses with access to adequate and affordable financial services that overcome traditional barriers such as high operating costs or a lack of credit history [12]. The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) are driving this development by providing digital solutions such as mobile applications, peer-to-peer lending, microfinance, and more to decrease geographical boundaries and serve underserved communities [4] [13]. AI-driven robo-advisor (RA) is making a crucial contribution to inclusion by offering automated financial planning services with cheaper cost. Hence democratizing professional portfolio management for the masses market [8]. This accessibility allows smaller investors to make wise investment decisions that were used to reserved for institutional players [13].

H2: RA has a significant relationship with FI

D. Investment Habit

Investment habits (IH) encompass the processes and decisions that individuals use in managing their finances to achieve long-term financial goals which might include the frequency of investing, diversification, strategies used, etc [14]. This behavior is significantly influenced by a combination of financial literacy and FinTech adoption as well as the investor's investment preferences. Higher financial literacy correlates with more active and diversified investment practices where it allows investors to better understand risks and opportunities that lead to more disciplined decisions [12]. FinTech adoption especially through tools such as robo-advisors (RA) improving it through convenient access to investment products and personalized recommendations at a lower cost. Moreover, individuals' investment preferences play a crucial role in shaping their investment patterns in selecting suitable assets [9] [11].

H3: RA has significant relationship with IH

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study implements quantitative methodology to empirically test the hypothesized impact of AI-powered robo-advisors on retail investors' financial literacy, financial inclusion, and investment habits. Primary data

TABLE I: Research Gaps

Topic of the Paper/Research	Methodology	Conclusion	Identified Gap
Understanding of Financial RA in Indonesia [6]	Descriptive exploratory method, benchmarking	Describes features & flow of early Indonesian RAs (Bibit, Bareksa).	Focuses on features, not user adoption factors or impact of specific Indonesian platforms.
Impact of RA on Financial Advice Market [8]	Literature review & conceptual framework	RAs democratize advice, lower costs, reach underserved segments.	Needs empirical testing on how much RA increase participation vs. serving existing investors, esp. in emerging markets.
Financial Literacy & Portfolio Diversification [10]	Quantitative survey analysis (SCF)	Higher FL strongly associated with greater portfolio diversification.	Focuses on traditional methods; doesn't examine how Fintech tools (RA) mediate the FL-diversification link.
FL, Education, & Downstream Behaviors [19]	Meta-analysis	FL/education have a surprisingly weak positive effect on actual financial behaviors.	Doesn't explore why the link is weak or what other factors (biases, context, tools) dominate behavior.
Impact/Role of RAs among Indonesian Investors [7]	Mixed methods	Gen Z uses RAs but may disregard advice.	Needs broader study on why Gen Z disregards advice & long-term impact on habits/well-being

was collected through questionnaire with Likert scaler from 1-5 which received 415 valid responses. The data is analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). PLS-SEM is statistical technique selected for its ability to estimate complex models with multiple latent variables.

The collected information is accessible as dataset on <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17431176>.

Majority of the respondents are predominantly female (58.6%) and consists mainly of young adults. The largest age group is 23-27 years old (41.4%) with the 28-32 age bracket following closely (34.6%). This population is highly educated, a clear majority hold a Bachelor's degree (S1) (56.3%) and with a significant portion also holding postgraduate degrees (S2/S3) (19.4%).

This educational background aligns with their professional status as 66.5% of the participants are employed. In terms of monthly income, the largest segment earns between Rp3,000,000 and Rp7,000,000 (41.8%), followed by those earning between Rp7,000,000 and Rp10,000,000 (31.9%). Geographically, the respondents are concentrated in major urban cities primarily Jakarta (19.8%), Denpasar (13.3%), and Surabaya (7.6%).

Fig. 1: Conceptual Model

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

To assess the variables of the measurement model, we evaluated both internal consistency reliability and convergent validity. Internal consistency reliability was confirmed valid as all constructs exceeded the recommended 0.70 threshold [15]. For example, Cronbach's Alpha values ranged from 0.749 to 0.867 while Composite Reliability (ρ_c) values ranged from 0.716 to 0.786. The result demonstrate strong consistency among the indicators for each latent variable.

The analysis of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) with all constructs surpassing the required minimum value

TABLE II: Construct Reliability and Convergent Validity

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability (ρ_c)	Composite Reliability (ρ_A)	AVE
FI	0.867	0.724	0.723	0.697
FL	0.749	0.712	0.716	0.710
IH	0.821	0.786	0.758	0.702
RA	0.804	0.799	0.759	0.757

of 0.50 [15]. The AVE values are ranging from 0.697 to 0.757 which indicate that each construct explains a substantial majority of the variance in its respective indicators. These results affirm that the measurement model is reliable and valid for the subsequent structural model analysis [16].

Furthermore, the assessment of discriminant validity was conducted utilizing the Fornell-Lacker criterion. This procedure is done to confirm that each latent variable is empirically distinct from the other constructs within the structural model [15]. This outcome proves that each construct shares more variance with its own indicators than it does with any other construct, confirming its uniqueness.

The results of the Fornell-Lacker analysis support the discriminant validity of the measurement model. Specifically, for Financial Inclusion (FI) (0.835) exceeded its highest correlation (0.797 with RA). Similarly, the Financial Literacy (FL) (0.843) was greater than its correlation with IH (0.809), and for Robo-Advisor (RA) (0.870) surpassed its correlation with FI (0.797). As this condition was met for all latent variables, discriminant validity is established.

TABLE III: Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

Construct	FI	FL	IH	RA
FI	0.835			
FL	0.704	0.843		
IH	0.722	0.809	0.838	
RA	0.797	0.785	0.714	0.870

Following the validation of the measurement model, the analysis proceeds to the evaluation of the structural model. To test the statistical significance of the hypothesized paths, a bootstrapping procedure was executed using SmartPLS 4.0. This non-parametric resampling technique is essential for estimating the precision of the PLS path estimates.

The procedure was specified to generate 5000 subsamples by drawing cases randomly from the original dataset. The PLS algorithm was then run on each of these

subsamples to create an empirical sampling distribution for each path coefficient.

TABLE IV: Path Coefficients and Significance

Path	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	t-statistics (O/STDEV)	p-values
RA \rightarrow FI	0.428	0.433	0.132	3.242	0.001
RA \rightarrow FL	0.407	0.412	0.127	3.205	0.001
RA \rightarrow IH	0.206	0.210	0.142	1.451	0.147

The analysis confirmed a positive and statistically significant relationship between **Robo-Advisor Adoption (RA) and Financial Inclusion (FI)**. The path coefficient was substantial ($\beta = 0.428$) and the result was highly significant ($t = 3.242$, $p = 0.0012$). This provides strong empirical support for H1.

This finding implies that Robo-Advisor technology acts as a significant catalyst for financial inclusion. In practical terms, these platforms appear to be successfully lowering traditional barriers that have excluded individuals from capital market participation [3] [4] [7]. These barriers usually include high advisory fees and the perceived complexity of financial products [12].

Hence, the result supports the “democratization of finance” narrative often attributed to FinTech innovations [9]. This finding also aligns with the finding suggesting that FinTech serves as a crucial tool to reach *unbanked* and *underbanked* populations by extending the reach of financial system [17]. This analysis provides evidence for this claim in the investment sector by showing that technology can significantly enhance participation in asset markets [5].

A similar finding is seen on the relationship between **Robo-Advisor Adoption (RA) and Financial Literacy (FL)** that turned out to be positive and statistically significant ($\beta = 0.407$, $t = 3.205$, $p = 0.0014$). This is an insightful finding as it suggests that Robo-Advisor are not merely tools that only executes commands [2] [7] [18]. Instead, their use is actively associated with an increase in their users’ financial literacy. This educational effect may be both direct and incidental. Directly, these platforms guide users through interactive modules for various complex financial terms. [6].

By engaging with the platform, users are exposed to core financial concepts e.g. diversification, risk-return trade-offs, and long-term compounding [4]. This finding helps differentiate the *tool* (the Robo-Advisor) from the *outcome* (user knowledge) which explains that the technology can empower users not just by managing their money, but by making them more competent in their own financial understanding [4] [7] [8].

Contrary to the first two hypotheses, the analysis did not find a statistically significant relationship between the adoption of **Robo-Advisor Adoption (RA)** and **Investment Habit (IH)**. While the path coefficient was positive, it was weak ($\beta = 0.206$), and the p -value of 0.147 failed to meet the conventional $\alpha < 0.05$ significance threshold. Therefore, H3 is rejected.

This non-significant result is perhaps the most intriguing finding of the study. It rises another concern in the adoption of financial technology. A tool like Robo-Advisor does not automatically create a behavioral habit [5] [19]. While this research shows that Robo-Advisor are effective at bringing people *into* the financial system (FI) and improving their *knowledge* (FL), it appears they do not have the *disciplined behavior* of a regular investment habit (IH). This points to a study in behavioral economics about the “intention-action gap” [20]. An individual may *download* the app (adoption) and *intend* to invest regularly, but they may fail to overcome behavioral hurdles like procrastination or present-bias [4] [5] [21].

Fig. 2: Graphic model of the analysis

Finally, establishing an investment habit is a complex psychological process that requires more than just a user-friendly interface [22]. This ensure us that while technology can solve for access and information but, the behavioral aspect of personal finance remains a distinct and significant challenge to solve [19] [23]. This also in line with analysis that show a surprisingly weak link between financial literacy and actual financial behavior which imply that other psychological factors are at play [19]. This result suggests a clear path for future research and a challenge for FinTech developers to bridge the gap by integrating more effective behavioral implementation

and self-control mechanisms into their digital platforms [4] [8] [23].

V. CONCLUSION

The research explored the impact that Artificial Intelligence (AI) driven Robo-Advisor (RA) rule on key aspects of personal finance within young and digitally-savvy population yet facing low capital market participation. The evolution of AI to deep learning models has enabled innovations like Robo-Advisor which offer automated portfolio management. These platforms leverage AI, machine learning, and big data to enhance operational efficiency and decision accuracy, although challenges related to model transparency and algorithmic bias remain considerations.

The study empirically tested the direct influence of RA adoption on Financial Inclusion (FI), Financial Literacy (FL), and Investment Habit (IH). Financial Literacy is defined as the knowledge and skills for well-knowledge financial decision-making, and Financial Inclusion as the equal access to adequate and affordable financial services. The two were found to be significantly and positively impacted by the use of Robo-Advisor. These findings support the statement that Robo-Advisor serve as effective tools for expanding the reach of the financial system to underserved underbanked populations and simultaneously enhancing the masses understanding of financial concepts through their interactive platforms. This aligns with the broader purpose of FinTech to improve the financial accessibility and empowerment.

However, a crucial and perhaps the most insightful finding is found regarding Investment Habit which infer to the disciplined and regular behaviors associated with achieving long-term financial goals. The analysis revealed no statistically significant relationship between Robo-Advisor adoption and the formation of Investment Habits. This result point out a critical distinction that while RA successfully lower barriers to access (FI) and improve knowledge (FL), they do not automatically create the behavioral discipline required for consistent investing (IH). This is also discussed in the concept of “intention-action gap” in behavioral economics where access to tools and information does not necessarily translate into sustained action due to psychological hurdles like procrastination or other. Establishing investment habits remains a complex cross section of knowledge, access, preferences, and self-control that needs to be explored further.

In conclusion, Robo-Advisor represents a significant advancement in financial services by demonstrably enhancing financial inclusion and literacy among the younger and digital literate demographic in rapid markets like

Indonesia. Yet, their limitation in directly trigger investment habits explains the importance of behavioral factors in personal finance. Future developments is needed in FinTech to address the behavioral aspect that can bridge the gap between providing access and initiate sustained action. Furthermore, helping users not only to start investing but to continue doing so consistently towards their long-term goals.

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